

Municipal Solid Waste Management in Special Economic Zone (SEZ) in North Thailand

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 16, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 17, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Municipal Solid Waste Management, Special Economic Development Zone, SWOT Analysis</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6557944</p>	<p><i>In the present era, municipal solid waste (MSW) is a huge issue to both the governance aspect and physical component. This research aims to investigate the municipal solid waste management (MSWM) in the Special Economic Zone (SEZ) of Chiang Rai Province using Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis. The economic growth of SEZ areas was increased of the number of tourists, and investment as well as the MSW problems. The results of SWOT analysis was indicated that the budget for MSWM was adequate, but the technology for waste collection, separation, and disposal method were a drawback of MSWM in SEZ. The public participation in MSWM system was effective factor to strategic planning especially in local administration level. Providing the knowledge of 3Rs (reduce, reuse, and recycle), and zero-waste policy to community network, it was enhanced the public awareness in MSW separation at sources which resulting in reduce the amount of MSW was transferred to final disposal or landfill site. These findings may help to establish a SWM practical and effective policy applied in SEZ areas.</i></p>

Introduction

Municipal solid waste (MSW) is significant issues impact on many aspects of economic, cultural, and life behaviours in all around the worlds including Thailand. In 2020, Thai government reports that Thailand's waste generated a total of 27.35 million tonnes/year and reduce from 2019 about 4% cause of COVID-19 pandemic and generation rate was 1.17 kg/capita/day. Only 11.19 million tonnes/year were appropriated disposal method. Approximately 11.93 million tonnes of MSW generated was processed for recycling, and 4.23 million tonnes was improperly disposed such as open burning and open dumping, that was negative affected on human health and environment (Pollution Control Department, 2020). Thailand has the policy to promote waste reduction and separation at source. The top-down policy approached on local administration was focused on sustainable environmental management and attached to the sustainable development goals (Acheampong et al., 2017; Schreiber et al., 2019). In the present year, Thailand's government has policy to establish and development of special economic zones (SEZs) for trade promotion, investment, marketing, and development to the ASEAN community (Chiang Rai Provincial Office of Local Administration, 2017; Chiang Rai Special Economic Zone, 2019). The SEZ is an area in which the business and trade laws are different from the rest of the country. The aims of SEZ was increased trade balance, employment, investment, job creation and effective administration. The creation of SEZ was taken into positive and negative impacts such as economic growth, influx offoreign worker, and tourist. SEZ in Thailand was operated in ten provinces which covered all region of Thailand, and Chiang Rai province was one province of SEZs. The geographical location of Chiang Rai province was attractive for business investment and tourist's destination cause beautiful place (Tengsak and Poboorn, 2015). In addition, Chiang Rai province has an accessibility in transportation and logistics by land and river with transportation hub. SEZ area of Chiang Rai province was covered three districts; Mae Sai, Chiang Saen, and Chiang Khong, where source of various goods and agricultural food products. SEZ in Chiang Rai province was generated MSW about 400,000 tonnes/year or 0.88 kg/capita/day and waste composition was divided into four types; organic waste, recycle waste, hazardous waste, and general waste (Chiang Rai Special Economic Zone, 2019). Previous study was reported that improper MSW approximately 150,000 tonnes/year in SEZ of Chiang Rai province (Manomaivibool et al., 2018). MSW management (MSWM) system was investigated by using several methods such as improving the collaboration and communication of waste to energy cluster (Beloborodko et al., 2015), strategies for businesses to adopt to climate change (Pesonen & Horn, 2014), a guideline and the efficient utilization of solid recovered fuel (Samolada & Zabaniotou, 2014), life cycle assessment (LCA) (Pesonen & Horn, 2014), multi-critical for a decision-making and others. Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis is one of the interesting tool for assessment of MSWM which was an effective and using for decision-making (Abdulredha et al., 2018; Byamba & Ishikawa, 2017; Chanthamixay et al., 2017; Paya, 2016; Alighadri & Rahmani, 2019; Mor et al., 2016). Recently, SWOT analysis was carried out in MSWM. In this study, MSW composition and generation were investigated current

situation and the MSWM data was collected by using questionnaire, field observation and in-depth interview key person in MSWM system in SEZ of Chiang Rai province. The questions were included the sustainable indicators including the social, economic, environmental aspects in MSWM. SWOT was analysed tool for investigated the MSWM system in study area. The result of the study was suggested the stakeholder for enhance the efficiency of MSWM system in SEZ.

Method

Study Area

The study area was SEZ in Chiang Rai province, Northern Thailand. The SEZ was covered of three districts in Chiang Rai province; Mae Sai, Chiang Saen, and Chiang Khong (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of SEZ in Chiang Rai Province

Data Collection

The background information of SEZ in Chiang Rai province was collected from primary and secondary data. The MSWM data including waste generation, waste collection, storage, transportation, separation and recycling, and disposal method was collected using questionnaire. The MSWM system such as integrated solid waste management (ISWM) center and disposal site, and operational method was collected by survey form. In-depth interview of MSWM system was focused on key person of MSW management (25 persons) which included the government officers, local authority and head of community. The scope of interview was focused on SWOT information of MSWM of SEZs in Chiang Rai province.

Data Analysis

The data was obtained from report, questionnaires, survey, and in-depth interview of SEZ in Chiang Rai province, was analyzed using SWOT. The results of SWOT could be useful for strategic planning of MSWM for the local government of SEZ in Chiang Rai province.

Ethical Considerations

This study was allowable by the Human Research Ethics Committee of Thammasat University (Science) (No.050/2563). The participants in this study were volunteers. Anonymity was conserved to protect the subjects' identities and confidential information.

Results and Discussion

Background Information and MSWM in SEZ

SEZ in Chiang Rai province was covered three districts; Mae Sai, Chiang Saen, and Chiang Khong. The population in SEZ area was approximately 186,573 people. The average province income based on gross national income (GNI) was 2,259.47 USD/capita/year or 67,786.10 THB/capita/year. The average population income of SEZ was highest in Mae Sai (3,005.2 USD/capita/year) and higher than GNI of average province income due to economic growth in SEZ area (Table 1). MSWM in SEZ was operated by local government. MSW generated in SEZ trends to increase with the number of population and economic growth. Chiang Rai is one destination of tourists from various countries. Therefore, the estimation of MSW was increased. Based on information of onsite observation and in-depth interview of key person (25 persons) as related to MSWM, the MSW generated in SEZ was generally collected 1-2 times/day depending on amount of MSW. ISWM center was operated in SEZ, and cause of odor problem which found during overload of MSW. The wastewater treatment system was operated for leachate and wastewater treatment generated from ISWM center. The final disposal after separated in ISWM center, the remaining waste was transferred to landfill site.

Table 1. Background Information and Generated MSW of SEZ in Chiang Rai Province

Description	SEZs		
	Mae Sai	Chiang Saen	Chiang Khong
Province income level average (USD/capita/year)	Gross national income (GNI) 2,259.47		
Population income average (USD/capita/year)	3,005.2	2,392.8	2,177.47
District income level	Low-middle	Low-middle	Low-middle
Total population of the city	76,489	48,138	61,946
MSW generation rate (kg/capita/year)	328.5	423.4	379.6
MSW generation rate (kg/capita/day)	0.90	1.16	1.04

MSW Generation

The MSW generation rate of SEZ in Chiang Rai province was investigated in Mae Sai, Chiang Saen, and Chiang Khong was found to be of 328.5 kg/capita/year (0.90 kg/capita/day), 423.4 kg/capita/year (1.16 kg/capita/day), and 379.6 kg/capita/year (1.04 kg/capita/day), respectively. This result was similarly to previous research about MSW generation rate in Chiang Saen district (Manomaivibool & Hempattarasuwan, 2014). Whereas, it was higher than the generation rate of Chiang Rai province; 0.88 kg/capita/day (Chiang Rai Provincial Office of Local Administration, 2017; Manomaivibool et al., 2018) and 0.8 kg/capita/day as study by Luz et al. (2021) in household area.

MSW Composition

The MSW composition was investigated in three districts of SEZ in Chiang Rai province. The MSW composition was categorized into four types of organic waste, recycle waste, hazardous waste, and general waste. The average composition of this study was organic waste (25.3±3.5%), recycle waste (16.5±4.1%), hazardous waste (6.7±4.7%), and general waste (51.5±5.8%), related to previous study (Suma et al., 2019). Organic and recycle wastes were highest about 29% and 20% in Mae Sai district, and general waste was highest in Chiang Saen district (57.5%) and Chiang Khong district (51%), and hazardous waste was highest in Chiang Khong district (12%) when compared with other areas (Figure 2).

Figure 2. MSW Composition of SEZs in Chiang Rai Province

MSW Collection and Transportation

The MSW collection and transportation in SEZ area was operated by local authority. The MSW collected from SEZ was commingle and non-commingle wastes. All MSW collected was transferred to ISWM center. The functional of ISWM center was separated recycling waste from other wastes and operated with manual and mechanical sorting. Then the remaining waste was transferred to dump truck and transport to landfill site. The disposal cost of MSW in SEZ was reduced with ISWM center operation when compared to without this center in previous (Nguyen-Trong et al., 2017; Pourhejazy et al., 2021). These result might be useful to planning the ISWM center in other SEZs.

MSW Disposal

Although the rejected MSW from ISWM center was transferred to landfill site, but these landfill was not sanitary like open dumping that can cause of environmental pollution such as soil and ground water contamination, dust, bad odor, and greenhouse gases emission (Swenson, 2007) (Figure 3). Additional, informal waste picker was separated the valuable waste at landfill site without personal health protection that leads to health hazard; such as respiratory disease, and cancer (Giusti, 2009; Parizeau, 2015; Haregu et al., 2016).

Figure 3. Open Dumping Site at Chiang Saen District

SWOT Analysis of MSWM in SEZ

The SWOT analysis of MSWM in SEZ, Chiang Rai province was obtained various stakeholder which included the local government officer, community leader, and representative from several group of residents (Tables 2). The SWOT matrix was included internal and external factors for analyzing (Table 3).

Table 2. SWOT Analysis of MSWM of SEZ in Chiang Rai Province

SWOT	Results
Internal factor	
Strengths (S)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Obvious of organization structure and job description for waste management 2. Emergency plan in case of fire at disposal site 3. ISWM center operation 4. Enough financial support 5. Pay attention on occupational and safety of worker/labor 6. Community participation for waste management 7. Promote waste reduction and separation at sources to community for composting and biogas production from organic waste 8. Operational committee of waste management 9. Work instruction of waste recycling 10. Waste collection and monitoring system 11. Waste treatment and disposal system operated with environmental concern 12. Knowledge of solid waste management
Weaknesses (W)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of public communication in waste segregation and waste recycling 2. Lack of awareness and participation of community 3. Lack of environmental monitoring at disposal site 4. Limitation of channel for communication 5. Lack of new technology for waste separation and disposal 6. Lack of planning in waste-to-energy
External factor	
Opportunities (O)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Holistic of waste management system (collection, transfer and transportation, sorting, and disposal) 2. Chiang Rai zero waste policy 3. Waste reduction at source policy 4. Road map of waste management in short term and long term 5. Cooperation with private sector for buying waste recycle 6. Commandment and policy of local government 7. Local administration place importance on solid waste management 8. Waste to energy plan
Threats (T)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discontinues of policy based on the executive change 2. Lack of the cooperation of private sector to hazardous waste management 3. No update of MSW database system 4. Lack of integration of nation and local regulations from top-down and bottom-up 5. Increase of solid waste with number of tourist 6. High cost for disposal and maintenance facility in waste management 7. Ineffective worker/labor for waste management 8. Operation cost not enough for waste management both public and private sectors 9. Ineffective of law and regulation enforcement in waste management

Table 3. SWOT Matrix of SEZs in Chiang Rai Province

SWOT Matrix	Indicator
SO	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enough financial support from government to education and enhance awareness in zero waste management policy through community structure 2. Obvious of organization structure and waste management monitoring

	system
	3. Local administration encourages waste management system; upstream (segregation), middle streams (recyclable), downstream (selling and community income)
ST	1. Establish solid waste segregation facilities for waste-to-energy policy 2. Planning policy in waste management system with all stakeholder (public and private sectors like informal recycling sector (IRS), and people in community) 3. Establish solid waste management center covering SEZs areas
WO	1. Provide the knowledge of MSWM in zero waste concept to people in community 2. Cooperate the stakeholders (public and private sectors, and community) to development of knowledge of waste management in household level and determine indicators for sustainability assessment in waste management system
WT	1. Provide and support budget to develop the MSWM model in sustainable development goals (SDGs) by all stakeholder

The SWOT analysis was help the organization assessment to improve their job. The SWOT information of MSWM was obtained from questionnaire, in-depth interview and field observation of SEZ in Chiang Rai province. The internal factor was strengths (S), the results shown that the local administration has readiness of human resources and facility for MSWM such as financial support and ISWM center. The weaknesses (W) of SEZ was lack of public communication for waste separation and recycling at source which resulted in low awareness of community. The old technology for MSWM and huge amount of final disposal were landfill. The characteristic of MSW can be used as a resource for energy production in waste-to-energy concept. In addition, the landfill construction was operated without environmental protection and monitoring, it just the open dumping site which cause of environmental pollution; leachate contamination, odor, and greenhouse gases emission. The external factor was opportunities (O), Chiang Rai province has a zero waste policy which was an opportunity to apply this concept in SEZ area. Currently, ISWM center was located in SEZ, which can be enhanced the efficiency of machine and technology for waste separation, recycling and recovery for other benefits; for example, refuse-derived fuel (RDF) (Suma et al., 2019). The threats (T) of MSWM was changed that depends on the head of executive in each administrative team. Law and regulation from top-down and bottom-up were not ineffective (Khan et al., 2016). Limitation area for new constructed landfill due to high cost of land area whereas the amount of MSW was continuously increased with the number of population in SEZ. Also, government and private sector was not linked and work cooperation.

The SWOT matrix was integrated of the strengths and opportunities (SO), strengths and treats (ST), weaknesses and opportunities (WO), and weaknesses and treats (WT). The SO strategy was using strengths to take advantage of opportunities by supply the budget from local administrative through head of community or network to enhance the educational and awareness of zero waste management. ISWM center located in SEZ was applied the new technology for waste recycling and recovery as well as find the benefit of rejected waste for energy resources which was supported to waste-to-energy concept (Sharma et al., 2018). The ST strategy was using strengths to avoid threats by using the zero waste and waste-to-energy policy to provide the knowledge in waste separation at source which helping the ISWM center to waste separation of other benefits. The promotion of 3Rs (reduce, reuse, and recycle) concept was reduced the MSW at source (Visvanathan et al., 2007; Chanhthaxay et al., 2017; Kotei et al., 2020). These strategies were reduced the final waste volume that transferred to the final disposal or landfill site. It could be solved the problem of limitation of land area from landfilling and reduce the operational cost (Daskalopoulos et al., 1998), also reduce the environmental pollution that emitted by not sanitary landfill such as open dumping (Paes et al., 2019). Establish the MSWM system by including all stakeholder especially private sector to support the new technology of MSWM due to private sector has power for investment (Yuan, 2013; Byamba & Ishikawa, 2017). The WO strategy was overcoming weaknesses by taking advantage of opportunities. Although, the knowledge of MSWM in community was low but Chiang Rai province has zero waste policy, therefore this policy could be applied for SEZ area. The determination of sustainable development indicators was included all stakeholders, it makes the benefit in process of decision making to planning or set-up the MSWM system in short-term or long-term (Shahba et al., 2017; Silva et al., 2020). The WT strategy was minimized weaknesses and avoid threats, to solve the problem of MSWM in SEZ, the government was provided and supported the budget to development the MSWM model with SDGs, and included all level of stakeholders in all processes. The SWOT analysis of MSWM was investigated by previous study, the public participation and communication to transfer policy from top-down and bottom-up for practice were influenced for sustainable development of waste management (Khan et al., 2016; Kotei et al., 2020; Siripattarachai, 2016). In addition, the level of knowledge was related to personal

awareness in waste management such as separation, reduce, reuse and recycle (Pasukphun et al., 2018; Alighadri & Rahmani, 2019). Otherwise, the main point of threats and weakness were cost, supply chain logistic, seasonal, lack of regulation and technical standard within the same policy framework (Haregu et al., 2016; Paes et al., 2019).

Conclusion

The SEZ was individual management and specific law and policy in special area. Therefore, the administration of SEZ was employed to flexible management. The results of this study was presented both positive and negative factors from SWOT analysis, which was challenged to improve the MSWM in SEZ areas. The increased of MSWM efficiency, not only financial support and policy but also providing the knowledge to enhanced awareness. Additional, public participation was an important to determine strategic planning of MSWM. The results of this study based on SWOT analysis and matrix might be useful to development of ISWM model and suggested the solution of MSWM in SEZ, Chiang Rai province.

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